

Antecedent of Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping in Indonesia

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the mediating effect of Trust in the relationship between Perceived Website Quality (PWQual), eWOM, and Perceived Benefits on Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping in Indonesia. The sample in this research are online shopping consumers in Indonesia there 118 respondents. The design research used a survey model purposive sampling method as a sampling technique. The data analyze in this research used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) as an analysis technique with AMOS as analysis tools. This research shows that : Perceived Website Quality has a significant effect on Perceived Benefits and Trust, Perceived Benefits and Trust has a significant effect on Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping, Perceived Website Quality has a significant effect on Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping through Trust.

Keywords: Perceived Website Quality, Perceived Benefits, eWOM, and Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping.

I. Introduction

The number of internet users in Indonesia has increased every year, according to the Association of Indonesian Internet Network Provider or APJII (Asosiasi Penyedia Jaringan Internet Indonesia) in a survey entitled "Internet User Penetration and Behavior in 2017". In addition to the use of social media, e-commerce sector and creative industries play an important role in increasing the number of internet users in Indonesia [5]. One of the marketing innovations that get attention from Indonesian people is online shopping trend using information technology called e-commerce. E-commerce is a process for purchases, sales, and marketing of products or services through electronic systems [39]. Tokopedia, Bukalapak, Lazada, BliBli, JD.ID, and Shoppe are the most visited or popular e-commerce in Indonesia [13].

According to the theory of planned behavior (TPB) model, behavioral beliefs that refer to someone's inner beliefs about the consequences of taking certain actions will influence attitudes toward actual behavior [1]. Meanwhile, according to the technology acceptance model (TAM) explains factors that can influence a person's attitude and behavior in using information technology. Technology acceptance model (TAM) is generally used to examine a person's perception or attitude in using information technology. By using the TAM model, this research can analyze and show that information technology can improve someone's work becomes more effective and efficient [10]. This research provides empirical validation of the antecedents of consumer attitudes toward online shopping and also examines the influence of perceived website quality in terms of interactivity and usability affect perceived benefits, electronic word of mouth (eWOM), trust, and attitude toward online shopping in Indonesia.

II. Literature Review

1.1. Perceived Website Quality

Perceived website quality can be measured by how users get benefits [3]. Based on the exploratory factor analysis, perceived website quality is divided into 4 dimensions: technical coverage, quality of content, specific content (service), and perceived quality. Perceived website quality as a measure which is consumers feel that the features and characteristics of the website complied with the requirements and consumer needs [21].

1.2. eWOM (Electronic Word of Mouth)

eWOM activities can create negative or positive statements made by actual, potential or previous consumers about products or companies, which is made available to a multitude of people and institution via the internet [20]. eWOM (electronic word of mouth) is an extrinsic requirement for consumers [19]. The existences of the internet are creating a new paradigm in communication and word of mouth is the beginning of the emergence electronic word of mouth [9].

1.3. Perceived Benefits

Perceived benefits are consumer perceptions of the overall quality or superiority of goods or services related to the intended intentions and expectations [35]. Perceived benefits as the sum of benefits that can meet consumer needs [40]. Perceived benefits in the context of this research as consumer trust about the extent to which consumers are better when making online transactions with certain websites [23].

1.4. Trust

Trust is an important thing to support the benefit relationship [6]. Benefit relationship based on trust is a measure of significance in describing several things such as cooperation, commitment, relationship duration, and quality. Given the complexity and the multidimensionality of the concept [18], someone can find several and different definitions of trust in the relevant literature. Trust is the willingness of a party to be vulnerable to the actions of another party based on the expectations that the other will perform a particular action important to the trustor [28]. Trust can also be referred to as an individual's trust in others determined by competence and perceived integrity [29].

1.5. Attitude

The definition of attitude is an affection of a person to accept or reject an object or behavior and measured by using a procedure that places a person on two-sided evaluative scale, for example, good or bad, agree or disagree, etc [2]. Definition of attitude is an overall evaluation of a person from a concept. Two types of attitudes that can be identified, there are attitudes toward objects and attitudes toward behaviors. Consumer's attitude in conducting online shopping is determined by several factors, such as access convenience, information convenience, transaction convenience, and individual satisfaction [30]. As in this study, the authors measured the attitudes of consumers towards online shopping in Indonesia, the attitude toward behaviors was the most relevant thing in the context of this research. Attitude toward behavior refers to the degree to which a person has a favorable or unfavorable evaluation or appraisal of the behavior to be followed up [36].

III. Hypotheses Development and Empirical Research Model

1.1. The Relationship between Perceived Website Quality and Perceived Benefits

Previous research shows that higher consumer perceptions of the quality of online shopping sites will affect consumer attitudes due to the fulfillment of consumer needs when using online shopping [4]. The quality of a website has a significant effect on perceived usefulness [26]. When consumers have an assessment of an online shopping site that has a website design features that is accordance with consumer needs, it will have an impact on increasing consumer perceptions of the perceived benefits of using these online shopping sites. Based on the description above the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H1 : Perceived Website Quality positively affects Perceived Benefits.

1.2. The Relationship between Perceived Website Quality and eWOM

The website quality is positively related to eWOM [32]. The previous study shows that when consumers perceived the quality of an online shopping website to be high in term of design, navigation, and search facilities, they would be more encouraged to post positive eWOM comments in website columns or social media recommendations. The website that has good reputations have a higher effect on eWOM [33]. Based on the description above the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H2: Perceived Website Quality positively affects eWOM.

1.3. The Relationship between Perceived Website Quality and Trust

Good website quality will increase consumer trust when making purchases online [29]. The importance of perceived website quality is to explain some of the variances in the construct of consumer trust [38]. The construct of perceived web quality, among three constructs, has a strong influence on consumer trust in online shopping sites [21]. Based on the description above the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H3: Perceived Website Quality positively affects Trust.

1.4. The Relationship between Perceived Benefits and Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping

Perceived benefits are something that associated with convenience and time savings or time efficiency carried out by the consumer [24]. Perceived benefits associated with online shopping sites, the result show that adopting and linking traditional sales systems to online sales systems is one of the key factors to getting the perceived benefits [11].

Therefore the benefits of an online shopping system show significant incentives to consumers and help in forming positive consumer attitudes toward online shopping sites. In the context of e-commerce, previous research has highlighted the significant role perceived benefits can play in explaining consumer attitude [23]. Based on the description above the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H4: Perceived Benefits positively affects Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping.

1.5. The Relationship between eWOM and Trust

Based on previous research, eWOM communication has a significant role in shaping and influencing internet users' attitudes and behavioral intentions [22]. eWOM as any positive or negative statement made by potential, actual, or former customers about a product or company which is made available to a multitude of the people and institutes via the Internet. eWOM communication is a phenomenon of consumers who use the internet to find relevant information [20]. Based on the description above the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H5: eWOM positively affects Trust

1.6. The Relationship between Trust and Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping

Prior e-commerce research has highlighted the importance of trust as a determinant of a consumer's attitude purchasing intention [27]. Trust can be described as an expectation that others will not behave opportunistically [15], and that the vendor will provide what has been promised [14]. Despite the variety of definitions, trust is generally considered important in online environments because of associated risks in such contexts [37]. Based on the description above the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H6: Trust positively affects Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping.

The aim of this study is to explain the effect of Perceived Website Quality, Perceived Benefits, EWOM, and Trust on Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping. Based on literature reviews and previous studies, the research framework is constructed based on Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) approach and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) approach. This study explains how Perceived Website Quality has an important role in influencing Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping. Based on the research hypothesis above model research can be developed as follows:

Figure 1 Conceptual Research Model

IV. Hypotheses Development and Empirical Research Model

1.1. Research Design

The object in this study are consumer attitudes towards online shopping in Indonesia are influenced by perceived website quality and mediated by perceived benefits, eWOM, and trust. While the subjects in this study are consumers of various types of products that use the internet as a means of buying or spending all kinds of goods for their needs on online shopping sites that they believe are trusted online shopping in Indonesia. In the process of collecting data, researchers used survey models and purposive sampling techniques as sampling techniques. The final stage of the study, researchers used AMOS as a data analysis tool.

1.2. Variable Definitions and Measurement

To test the hypotheses model, a survey questionnaire was designed on the basis of comprehensive literature reviews to specify a set of items that ensured content validity. The data collection technique in this study is by distributing offline questionnaire forms and online questionnaires through Google form by contacting personally to

consumers who purchase products through online shopping sites in Indonesia. The question items in the questionnaire were prepared using a five-scale model that refers to the Likert scale to obtain interval data. The five-scale model is designed to test how strongly the research subjects "strongly agree" do or even "strongly disagree" by giving answer choices in the form of strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree [16]. This research used self-reported questionnaires to measure Perceived Website Quality, Perceived Benefits, eWOM, Trust and Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping.

Perceived Website Quality. Website functionality includes usability and interactivity when consumers make purchases on online shopping [8]. All constructs of Perceived Website Quality were measured with the five-scale model that refers to the Likert scale to obtain interval data. The measurements were assessed via five-scale (1 - 5) item rating scales ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" of four indicators: online shopping site catalog, fast loading catalog, requires effort in search and good website design.

eWOM. The electronic word of mouth is an important message for consumers when consumers want to get information about the quality of a product or service to make a purchase decision [7]. All constructs of eWOM were measured with the five-scale model that refers to the Likert scale to obtain interval data. The measurements were assessed via five-scale (1 - 5) item rating scales ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" of three indicators: the intensity of recommendations, positive comments and consumer intensity in reading reviews.

Perceived Benefits. Positive or negative perception of consumers based on how much benefits are felt [12]. All constructs of Perceived Benefits were measured with the five-scale model that refers to the Likert scale to obtain interval data. The measurements were assessed via five-scale (1 - 5) item rating scales ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" of three indicators: online shopping security, shop anytime and minimize the possibility of buying unnecessary items.

Trust. The high level of uncertainty and the dynamics that exist in cyberspace (internet), trust is a determinant of one's immediate attitude [15]. All constructs of Trust were measured with the five-scale model that refers to the Likert scale to obtain interval data. The measurements were assessed via five-scale (1 - 5) item rating scales ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" of four indicators: transaction security, protected from hackers, digital security certificates and the provider not selling personal information.

Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping. The individual's positive or negative evaluation of a relevant behavior and is composed of an individual's salient beliefs regarding the perceived consequences of performing a behavior [25]. All constructs of Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping were measured with the five-scale model that refers to the Likert scale to obtain interval data. The measurements were assessed via five-scale (1 - 5) item rating scales ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree" of three indicators: good idea, better than conventional and fun shopping.

V. Research Sample

Data gathering was conducted through questionnaires distribution and Google form. The number of total respondents was 145; they were the respondents who use online shopping sites to purchase goods more than once to fill out the distributed questionnaires. Based on the survey, there were 135 questionnaires which are completely filled out with the level of percentage was 93.1 percent from the total respondents. There were 135 questionnaires used in this study. However, during data processing, the extreme value was 17 questionnaires, so they were eliminated from the research sample. The total samples of this study were 118 respondents. The data were gathered from online shopping consumers in Indonesia until 2018.

The hypotheses test in this study used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach. SEM was used to test the causality relation between Perceived Website Quality, Perceived Benefits, eWOM, Trust and Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping constructs. The test using SEM consists of two kinds of variables, i.e. observable/manifest variable; and latent/non-observable variables. Observable variable is the indicator which is reflected from construct and latent variable is developed from a construct theory. In evaluating the fit of the model, several goodness-of-fit indices were used; those are normal fit index (NFI); comparative fit index (CFI); Tucker-Lewis index (TLI); root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) in addition to the X^2 statistic.

Table 1 Scale Item for Measures

Reflective scale names and items (measured 5-point scale indicating the extent to which respondent agrees with following statements)	Standardized factor loading
Perceived Website Quality(Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.852$, VE = 0.656, CR = 0.855, DV = 0.810)	
Catalogs on online shopping sites can meet consumer needs.	0.734
Load faster catalogs on websites.	0.825
Requires a little effort to find what consumers need.	0.713
Overall, online shopping websites are very well designed.	0.811
eWOM (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.911$, VE = 0.803, CR = 0.915, DV = 0.896)	
Consumer often read online recommendations to buy products from this online catalog retailer.	0.890
Positive comments help consumers when purchasing products at online shopping.	0.850
Positive reviews help consumers when purchasing products.	0.913
Perceived Benefits (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.818$, VE = 0.670, CR = 0.826, DV = 0.818)	
With the catalog of products displayed on online shopping sites, consumers can shop safely anywhere.	0.852
Consumers can make purchases online at the time whenever consumers want.	0.749
Buying products on online shopping sites minimize the possibility of consumers making unnecessary purchases.	0.745
Trust (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.832$, VE = 0.629, CR = 0.834, DV = 0.793)	
Consumers feel safe when making payments and making financial transactions on online shopping sites.	0.610
Online shopping sites will protect consumers related to my financial data from hacker attacks.	0.843
Online shopping sites provide facilities for Digital Security Certificates (SSL) on website systems that consumers use in financial transactions.	0.878
Online shopping sites do not sell consumer personal information such as email addresses, telephone numbers, names and identity numbers to other parties for commercial purposes.	0.632
Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.761$, VE = 0.607, CR = 0.770, DV = 0.779)	
Online shopping is a good idea to do.	0.668
Shopping online is better than shopping offline or conventional.	0.604
Online shopping is a fun thing to do.	0.889

(Note : VE = Variance Extracted; CR = Construct Reliability; DV = Discriminant Validity)

Table 1 explains the information about the difference of each construct and the question item used, the Cronbach value α on each construct, the loading factor value of each construct should be more than 0.6 cut off point [17]. The test result of construct validity value, variance extract, and discriminant validity in Table 1 shows that the result that the construct of Perceived Website Quality, eWOM, Perceived Benefits, Trust and Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping discriminant validity (DV) are based on the determined statistics cut off value that is construct reliability (CR) was more than 0.7, the variance extract (VE) was more than 0.5, and discriminant validity (DV) was more than 0.7.

VI. Result and Discussion

In order to test empirical research and the difference hypotheses against the structure model, covariance-based path estimation was used, namely structural equation modeling (SEM) based on the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (Nuryakin et al., 2018). In this study, there were four results of the analysis that met the goodness of fit test criteria; RMSEA=0.075, CMIN/DF=1.656, TLI=0.920, and CFI=0.934. While the analysis results that do not meet the goodness of fit test criteria; Chi Square=187.148, P=0.000, GFI=0.846, and AGFI=0.792.

The empirical model illustrated in Figure 2 has six hypothesized relationship among the variables; Perceived Website Quality, eWOM, Perceived Benefits, Trust and Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping. Figure 2 shows the path diagram resulting from the structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis using AMOS software. This study provides an empirical model that the result shows that Trust is mediating the relationship between Perceived Website

Quality on Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping in Indonesia. Other findings show that the relationship between Perceived Website Quality on eWOM and the relationship between eWOM on Trust has no significant effects.

Hypothesis 1 is supported, which indicates that there a positive impact between Perceived Website Quality on Perceived Benefits. The statistical result shows that hypotheses 1 are significant (coefficient = 0.000, $p < 0.05$).

The result did not support hypotheses 2, which stated that the impact of Perceived Website Quality on eWOM. The statistical result shows that hypotheses 2 are insignificant (coefficient = 0.966, $p > 0.05$).

Hypothesis 3 is supported, which indicates that the impact of Perceived Website Quality on Trust. The statistical result shows that hypotheses 3 are significant (coefficient = 0.000, $p < 0.05$).

Hypothesis 4 is supported, which indicates that the impact of Perceived Benefits on Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping. The statistical result shows that hypotheses 4 are significant (coefficient = 0.002, $p < 0.05$).

The result did not support hypotheses 5, which stated that the impact of eWOM on Trust. The statistical result shows that hypotheses 5 are insignificant (coefficient = 0.648, $p > 0.05$).

Hypothesis 6 is supported, which indicates that the impact of Trust on Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping. The statistical result shows that hypotheses 6 are significant (coefficient = 0.000, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 2 Hypothesis Test Result

However, note that the relationship between Perceived Website Quality on eWOM and eWOM on Trust are insignificant regardless of the Trust context.

Table 2 Summary of Results from The SEM Models

Relationship	Path Coeff.	CR	Prob.	Hypotheses
Perceived Website Quality ----- Perceived Benefits	0.737	6.959	0.000	Supported
Perceived Website Quality ----- eWOM	0.004	0.042	0.966	Not Supported
Perceived Website Quality ----- Trust	0.753	6.076	0.000	Supported
Perceived Benefits ----- Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping	0.309	3.076	0.002	Supported
eWOM ----- Trust	0.036	0.456	0.648	Not Supported
Trust ----- Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping	0.757	5.089	0.000	Supported

Table 2 showed that Perceived Website Quality directly effects on Perceived Benefits ($\beta=0.737$, $CR=6.959$, $p<0.05$), it means that hypotheses 1 is supported. Perceived Website Quality has an insignificant effect directly to the eWOM with the value ($\beta=0.004$, $CR=0.042$, $p>0.05$). However, the test result showed that probability > 0.05 which means that Perceived Website Quality insignificant effect on eWOM. Furthermore, hypotheses 2 are not supported. Perceived Website Quality has a direct effect on Trust with the value ($\beta=0.753$, $CR=6.076$, $p<0.05$). However, the Perceived Website Quality is significant to influence on Trust. Hence, hypothesis 3 is supported.

Perceived Benefits directly effects on Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping ($\beta=0.309$, $CR=3.076$, $p<0.05$), it means that hypotheses 4 is supported. eWOM has an insignificant effect directly to the Trust with the value ($\beta=0.036$, $CR=0.456$, $p>0.05$). However, the test result showed that probability > 0.05 which means that eWOM insignificant effect on Trust. Thus, the result of hypotheses 5 is not supported. Furthermore, Trust has a partial mediating effect on the relationship between Perceived Website Quality on Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping ($\beta=0.757$, $CR=5.089$, $p<0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 6 is supported.

VII. Conclusion

1.1. Theoretical and Practical Implication

To create a good perception of perceived website quality some things to do are designing a website system to display menus or catalogs of goods, make a website system that is easy to use, the website system must be fast loading when consumers make transactions, and the website system must be safe from hacker attacks. Perceived Website Quality can be measured by how users get benefits as meeting needs [3] and accordance with the results in this study. Therefore, this study shows that if Perceived Website Quality is good will have a significant effect on Perceived Benefits. This is evidenced from the results of this study which shows that by using online shopping consumers get convenience in shopping and service quality assurance from providers of online shopping sites such as financial transactions security, the authenticity of products, reliable freight forwarding facilities, and guaranteed return of goods if the item received is not in accordance with the order.

The development of marketing innovation has created a new paradigm called EWOM (Electronic Word of Mouth) in social media, but according to the results of this study, EWOM cannot be said as a determinant by consumers in making purchasing decisions. This is based on the findings of the author that EWOM can also be created intentionally and structured through fake accounts or endorsement to raise ratings instantaneously to be trusted by consumers. Some respondents in this study were also aware of this. The results in this study are different from the results in the prior research [32], that in the context of e-commerce it was revealed that website quality was positively related to eWOM. While based on this study, the authors found several respondents who didn't do a review of the quality of online shopping sites. Thus, this study shows that good Perceived Website Quality doesn't necessarily create positive comments on eWOM.

The quality of a website has an effect on consumer trust in online shopping sites [21]. In this study, Trust is an important variable because it directly affects the variable Consumer Attitudes towards Online Shopping. Without looking at reviews from other consumers or previous buyers in this study called eWOM, consumers can assess how the website quality and create a perception of trust for consumers. Thus, in this study shows that the Perceived Website Quality will have a significant effect on Trust.

With online shopping, consumers get benefits from a time-saving such as flexible and efficient in making purchases. Consumers only choose the products in the website system and the delivery of the products using courier services according to products purchased by consumers on online shopping sites. Based on the prior research, high perceived benefits measured by how high the comfort value and time savings or time efficiency carried out by consumers when making purchases in online shopping sites, then will create Consumer Attitudes Towards Online Shopping [24], and this statement is in accordance with the findings of this study. Thus in this study shows that Perceived benefits will have a significant effect on Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping. The results of this study show that consumers get benefits because with online shopping consumers get a convenience when purchasing of product in anytime and anywhere. Online shopping providers also offer free shipping and product discounts to make consumers more interested in shopping online.

According to the prior research, eWOM communication has emerged as a result of the increasing number of consumers using the internet to find relevant information such as online opinions and recommendations are considered credible and trusted by internet users [34]. While in this study the authors obtained a sample of respondents who didn't all read eWOM in the comments column or social media as a measure of their level of trust. Consumer trust in this study emerged from their assessment about the quality of online shopping sites and guaranteed quality of the products displayed on the sales menu. Most of the respondents in this study were more trusting in the quality aspects of online

shopping sites with guaranteed product authenticity and guaranteed delivery of products than believing in eWOM. Based on facts that have been found by authors shows that there are fake accounts to build consumer trust by giving positive comments in the comments column or social media. Thus, based on the result of this study shows that eWOM which contains positive comments does not affect on Trust.

Trust is also one of the determining factors in measuring consumer's desire when making purchases through online shopping. The high level of uncertainty and the dynamics that exist in cyberspace (internet), trust is a determinant of one's immediate attitude; these statements are accordance with the result of this study [15]. According to the perceptions of providers of online shopping, Trust is also proven to have a positive influence on Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping. This fact can be seen with the emergence of advertisements and endorsement to influence Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping by online shopping providers. Thus in this study shows that the high level of trust will have a significant effect on consumer attitudes towards online shopping. The results of this study show that according to the consumers, security in financial transactions is the most important thing. Securities facilities such as digital security certificates and hacker security protection are additional facilities to make consumers are Trust to an online shopping site.

In this study show that Trust is mediating Perceived Website Quality on Consumer Attitudes toward Online Shopping. The findings are proven by the results of path analysis that show the value of indirect effects of Perceived Website Quality on Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping through Trust is greater than the direct effects of Perceived Website Quality on Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping.

1.2. Limitation and Future Research

This study using 118 respondents, the author expects that in the further research it can expand the number of respondents and interview respondents about what reasons affect respondents when answering questions in the research questionnaire. The purpose of adding more samples than the sample in this research is because in further research the researcher can produce a more representative sample. Further researchers can also add or discard some variables in this research that are considered imperfect. The purpose of reduction or addition of variables is that the variables used to measure the attitude of consumers towards online shopping become more varied.

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